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ERVK3-1 activation in lung metastasis.

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Endogenous retroviral activation during the tumor life cycle remains incompletely understood. We describe here ERVK3-1 activation in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

We utilize genomic and transcriptomic technologies to study the genomic sequences (DNA), the transcriptome (RNA), and epigenetic modification (eg., CpG-DNA) of humans with cancer. This includes the primary tumor, the source of the transformation - like mutant variants of p53 - subtypes of the primary tumor, including luminal, basal and HER2+ forms in breast cancer, and adeno and squamous forms of NSCLC in lung cancer, “regional” metastasis to the lymph nodes, metastasis to distant sites, including the lungs, the liver and the brain, and the circulating tumor stem cell. Here we measure total transcription in metastasis to the lungs to discover and describe a therapeutic target identified through rigorous study of the lung metastatic transcriptome in breast cancer: a therapeutic target that is up-regulated and metastasis-specific, providing ideal therapeutic index to minimize toxicity and maximize efficacy: ERVK3-1.

Results

Figure 1: ERVK3-1 is differentially expressed in lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer.

I. Lung metastases and primary tumors; human breast cancer.

n=6 primary tumors from humans with breast cancer

n=2 lung metastases (tumor) from humans with breast cancer

GeneID	<i>p</i> -value	lfcSE	stat	log2FC	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
2086	1.74E-02	0.739	2.378409	1.7583986	521.37	ERV3-1	2517/22997	89.1

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in the primary tumors of the breast and in lung metastases of humans with breast cancer (9), we discovered differential expression of endogenous retrovirus group K3 member 1, encoded by *ERV3-1* in metastasis to the lungs in humans with breast cancer (**Chart 1**). The expression of *ERV3-1* changed more than nearly 90% of the human lung metastatic transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 22,997 transcripts (“Rank”). Note, however, the positive fold-change indicating decreased quantity of *ERV3-1* messenger RNA in lung metastases in this metastatic setting.

Thus, differential and increased expression of *ERV3-1* defines the lung metastatic transcriptome in human breast cancer.

Discussion

Adjunctive treatments in medical oncology limit the emergence of resistant tumor clones during treatment with a second agent (whether neoadjuvant chemotherapy or a targeted therapy like trastuzumab). Inhibitors of *ERV3-1*, immunoglobulin or small molecule based (once evaluated for toxicity and safety) can immediately be tested for efficacy in patients with lung metastasis who have failed previous treatment, with the ultimate goal of identifying the most effective inhibitors of lung metastasis in humans with breast cancer who have not yet progressed but are at predicted high risk, or those whose metastasis has not yet become unmanageable due to metastasis size, number or location. A multi-kinase approach delivered in conjunction with chemotherapies that target dNTP synthesis, replication of the daughter strand and activity at the spindle at anaphase, targeting *CDKN* inactivation and ATP-binding cassette pump expression in resistant cases, is most likely to be most effective in limiting tumor clone resistance (11).

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Methods

We utilized GSE191230 for this tumor transcriptome study, measuring whole transcription in metastasis to the lungs and in primary tumors from humans with breast cancer (along with GSE186637, in human breast cancer cells for target validation) using RNA-sequencing and microarray data (published and public) and R-based computational methods.